

Occurrence of Post Dural Puncture Headache in Patients Undergoing Lower Limb Surgery under Spinal Anaesthesia: A Descriptive Observational Study

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Abstract

Aims: Regional anaesthesia is preferred for many surgeries, more so for surgeries on the limbs. Surgeries below the umbilicus are usually done under spinal anaesthesia as it provides adequate intraoperative analgesia, muscle relaxation and reflex suppression. To understand the current status and magnitude of this problem in our set up, we conducted this descriptive observational study to see the occurrence of PDPH in patients of who had undergone lower limb surgery under spinal anaesthesia.

Methods and Material: The study was conducted in the department of anaesthesia, Department of orthopedic at S.M.S. hospital and trauma centre, attached to S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur. A Hospital based descriptive observational study. Sample size was calculated 729 cases and required at 95% confidence and 2% absolute error to verify the expected 9.5% PDPH in case of spinal anaesthesia.

Statistical Analysis: Data has been entered in excel and statistical analysis was performed with the SPSS, version 21 for Windows statistical software package (SPSS inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The Categorical data was presented as numbers (percent) and were compared among groups using Chi square test.

The quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation. Probability was considered to be significant if less than 0.05.

Conclusion: PDPH occurs more frequently when the number of prick are more than one other factor like age, sex, waist hip ratio, time to ambulation do not contribute substantially. 25G Quincke's needle is a good choice for successful, uneventful spinal anaesthesia in adequately trained hands (PDPH 1.2%) Also 25 G needles with Quincke type bevel are comfortable for training new post-graduates whereas finer needle may require introducer.

Keywords: PDPH, Lower limb surgery, Regional Anaesthesia, Anaesthetic complications.

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Introduction

Regional anaesthesia is preferred for many surgeries, more so for surgeries on the limbs. Surgeries below the umbilicus are usually done under spinal anaesthesia as it provides adequate intraoperative analgesia, muscle relaxation and reflex suppression.

By convention patients having undergone dural puncture for diagnostic or therapeutic regional anaesthesia are advised to stay recumbent for first 24 hrs after the procedure to avoid post dural puncture headache (PDPH). It is one of the most dreaded side effect of a very simple and effective anaesthesia technique, spinal anaesthesia. In the postoperative period it is comfortable if the patient can sit up to take medication, food and for parturients to feed the

neonates, but for the fear of PDPH patients are not permitted to sit up.

Spinal anaesthesia has several advantages, like decreased risk of failed intubation, aspiration of gastric contents, avoiding the use of depressant agents, decreased incidence of deep vein thrombosis and reduced intra-operative blood loss.

To understand the current status and magnitude of this problem in our set up, we conducted this descriptive observational study to see the occurrence of PDPH in patients of who had undergone lower limb surgery under spinal anaesthesia.

Material and Methods

Study Area: The study was conducted in the department of anaesthesia, Department of orthopedic at S.M.S. hospital and trauma centre, attached to S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur.

Study Design: A Hospital based descriptive observational study.

Study Period: Data collection was started after approval from research review board and Institutional Ethics Committee of S.M.S. Medical College Jaipur from December 2019 to November 2020.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated 729 cases and required at 95% confidence and 2% absolute error to verify the expected 9.5% PDPH in case of spinal anaesthesia.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Lower limb surgery under spinal anaesthesia.
2. Age group-20 to 50 yr.
3. ASA grade-I &II
4. Patients who give written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Uncooperative patients.
2. Patients with h/o headache.
3. Patients who have received spinal anaesthesia previously within one month.

Methodology

After obtaining approval from institutional Ethics Committee, this hospital based observational descriptive study was conducted. This study included 729 patients of ASA grade I and II age 20 to 50yr who had undergone lower limb surgery.

After pre- anaesthetic check-up, informed written consent and assessing fasting status, patients were

taken in the operation theatre, monitors were connected to patient and baseline Pulse rate, NIBP, SpO₂, ECG were recorded. IV line was secured with 18/20G intra venous (IV) cannula patients were coloaded with Ringer's lactated.

Patients included in the study were those who had received subarachnoid block by lumbar puncture in the sitting position at L3-L4 or L4-L5 level in the midline with a 25G Quincke's spinal needle. Monitoring was done using ECG, Heart Rate, NIBP, Pulse oximetry and recorded at interval 5minutes, 10minutes, 15minutes, and 20minutes. Level of sensory and motor block was assessed by pin prick method and patients were given oxygen at the flow rate of 4L/min by face mask. Hypotension was defined as a systolic arterial blood pressure (SABP) <90 mm of Hg or a decrease in SABP by 20% or more from the baseline value and was treated by IV fluids and incremental doses of inj. mephentermine 6 mg IV as required. Bradycardia was defined as fall in heart rate below 55 beats per minute and was treated with incremental doses of inj. atropine 0.3-0.6 mg IV. Respiratory depression was defined as a respiratory rate less than 8 breaths per minute and/or oxygen saturation less than 90% on room air.

Post-Operative Recordings: At the end of surgery, patients were shifted to the post-operative ward. Postoperatively, patients were observed at 24,48,72 hours and were assessed for any complaint of headache, its site (frontal, occipital, retro orbital and neck region), severity and exacerbated in sitting or standing and relieved by lying down and symptoms possibly associated with PDPH like nausea, vomiting and neck stiffness. The nature and severity of headache was assessed using the visual analog scale (VAS): 0 being no headache and 10 being worst imaginable headache. The most important criteria for classifying headache as PDPH was its postural nature. Transient headache limited to the day of surgery was not be considered as PDPH.

The grading of headache is defined as follows:

- Grade I (mild)-VAS Score 1-3
- Grade II (moderate)-VAS Score 4-7
- Grade III (severe)-VAS Score 8-10

Therapy with NSAIDs, caffeine and hydration was recommended to patients experiencing postural headache. Data collection was done by filling the proforma and attached.

Side effects: The following side effects were looked for:

Nausea and vomiting – assessed by three point scale.

- 0= no nausea and vomiting,
- 1= mild to moderate nausea or vomiting not needing treatment,
- 2= severe nausea or vomiting needing treatment

Any other complication and patient's complaints (if any).

Statistical Analysis: Data has been entered in excel and statistical analysis was performed with the SPSS, version 21 for Windows statistical software package (SPSS inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

The Categorical data was presented as numbers (percent) and were compared among groups using Chi square test.

The quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation. Probability was considered to be significant if less than 0.05.

Observations and Results: The present study included 729 patients who underwent lower limb injury in the age group of 20-50 years of ASA grade

I and II admitted in Trauma center and Dhanwantri hospital attached to S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur and scheduled for lower limb surgery under spinal anaesthesia after Obtaining written and informed consent.

Demographic Data

1. Age

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age (year)	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	322	44.17
31-40	209	28.67
41-50	198	27.16
Total	729	100

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Majority of the study population were in the age group of 20-30 year 322(44.17%) Which was followed by 31-40 year age group 209(28.67%) while least proportion of study population were in age group of 41-30 year 198 (27.16%). The mean age of study population was 34.16 years with standard deviation 9.49.

2. Gender

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	607	83.26
Female	122	16.74
Total	729	100

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to gender

Study population consisted of 607 males (83.26%) and 122 females (16.74%). male to female ratio was 4.95.

3. Waist Hip Ratio

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to WHR

Waist Hip Ratio	Frequency	Percentage
0.68 - 0.75	43	5.8%
0.76 - 0.80	81	11.11%
0.81 - 0.85	132	18.1%
0.86- 0.90	332	45.5%
0.91- 0.95	141	19.34%

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to WHR

Majority of the study population were in waist hip ratio 0.86 - 0.90 (45.5%) which was followed by 0.91 - 0.95 (19.34%) while least proportion of study population were in waist hip ratio 0.68 - 0.75 (5.8%). Mean waist hip ratio of 0.85 with standard deviation of 0.053.

4. Number of Pricks

Table 4: Occurrence of PDPH according to number of pricks

No. of Pricks	PDPH		Total
	Yes	No	
1	0	720	720
2	8	0	8
4	1	0	1
Total	9	720	729

$X^2= 649.294, DF=1, p \text{ value}= 0.001$

Figure 4: Occurrence of PDPH according to number of pricks

Maximum number of PDPH in study population was among patients with two attempt of prick 8 out of 8 patients, followed by patients with four attempts of prick one out of one, while there was none case of PDPH among patients with one attempt of prick. Association between attempts of prick and PDPH was statistically significant with X^2 value: 649.294, DF-1 and $p < 0.001$.

Discussion

Subarachnoid block is usually the anaesthesia of choice for infra umbilical surgeries in almost all age group. For orthopaedic surgery of lower limb subarachnoid block may be combined with a continuous epidural block. It has several advantages ease of performances, minimal hemodynamic changes (when judiciously perform), predictable duration, good operative conditions. Headache reported which did not fit into the above definition were not labelled as PDPH. We have considered – Age, Sex, Waist Hip ratio, multiple dural puncture. Body mass index was not considered as the patients were unable to stand and weigh themselves. Patients with medical history of headache were not included in this study.

Age: The overall occurrence of PDPH was observed to be 1.2% in our study. Patients were in the age group of 20 to 50years, the distribution was similar

in all age groups. 9 patients out of 729 developed PDPH. L. Chan et al (1992) reported incidence of 13.9% PDPH predominantly in the younger age group (<50 year) which is similar to ours but incidence is much higher than ours (1.2%), Although they have also used 25G Quincke needle but they have not mentioned the number of attempts taken for lumbar puncture. [13] Delpizzo K et al (2017) also observed the incidence of PDPH in 15-45 years age group with 27G Pencil point needle which was similar to ours (1.2%) with 25G Quincke needle. [27] L. Chan et al had observed that PDPH was more frequently seen below 50 years of age (85%) as compared to above 50 years (15%) of total cases of PDPH. [13]

We also have a similar observation. As all our patients were in age group of 20-50 years. PDPH was almost equally distributed in all the three decade and the P value (0.878) was not significant.

Gender: The gender distribution of our patients is in favour of males (607) as compared to Females (122). The reason is obvious as the study group consists of orthopedic patients predominantly trauma. As we all know the trauma is more frequently seen among males so the spectrum. Swapnil Meshram et al (2020) et al observed the incidence of PDPH 0.4% in males and 0.8% in females. Generally it is seen

that out of the total occurrence of PDPH it is more in the females. Our observation has been that 1.15% of the males out of 607 development PDPH where as 1.63% of females reported out of 122 which was statistically not significant (P value-0.996).

Waist Hip Ratio: Waist Hip Ratio is an indicator of fat distribution in individuals, it is an indirect indicator of obesity. As majority of our patients could not weigh and measure them to calculate BMI, so we did the WHR measurement. The Indian standards for waist hip ratio 0.89 in males, 0.81 in females, majority of our patients (81%) were within normal range (0.68 – 0.90), only 19 % had waist hip ratio in the range of (0.91 – 0.95). The occurrence of PDPH was proportionate in all the groups and was not clinically significant.

Needle size and type: We being a Government institute are routinely supplied with 25G Quincke bevel spinal needles for lumbar puncture, we do not usually have a choice of needle size or type. So we decided to observe the occurrence of PDPH in our set up which is 1.2%. Jawaharlal N. Irkal et al (2016) used 25G needle and observed PDPH in 18% with Quincke type and 2% with Whitacre needles with Quincke there is incidence substantially higher than ours. If judiciously used 25G Quincke needle have equally good result like finer and pencil point needle.

Number of pricks: A strong correlation has been observed with number of attempts done for spinal anaesthesia. In our own observation all the 9 patients who developed PDPH a successful block was done in two attempts. The rest 720 patients who did not report PDPH received block in single attempt. Similar observations were made by Kassa AA et al (2015) when they used needle less than 24G the incidence of PDPH was 8.3% and greater number of patients developed PDPH with multiple attempts which was statistically significant on multivariate analysis. Metanalysis Hong Xu et al suggested that use of extremely small sized spinal needle made result in higher incidence of PDPH because of multiple dural puncture resulting from technical difficulties. Swapnil Meshram et al did not find a statistically significant correlation with number of attempts. The other factors which they observed was a tension headache prior to spinal anaesthesia (p value < 0.01).

Conclusion

PDPH occurs more frequently when the number of prick are more than one. Other factors like age, sex, waist hip ratio do not contribute substantially. 25G Quincke's needle is a good choice for successful, uneventful spinal anaesthesia in adequately trained hands (PDPH 1.2%) Also 25 G needles with Quincke type bevel are comfortable for training new

post-graduates whereas finer needle may require introducer.

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